

INFLUENCE OF Fe, Mn, AND Cr ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF P DURING CARBOTHERMAL REDUCTION OF SYNTHETIC SLAGS

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Introduction

Within the integrated steel route, between 100 – 150 kg of basic oxygen furnace slag (BOFS) per tonne of produced crude steel occurs.¹ During oxygen blowing, unwanted steel constituents such as P mainly bound as $3\text{CaO}\cdot\text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ (C_3P), but also considerable amounts of Fe, Mn, and Cr enter the slag as oxides.^{2, 3} Downstream pyrometallurgical processes represent a potential solution to make these components available. Therein, a crucial step is the reduction of P-species, whereby highly reactive gaseous P originates. By contact with a metal bath, undesired phosphides are formed, reducing the metal phase's recyclability. The Chair of Thermal Processing Technology has developed an inductively heated packed bed reactor filled with graphite cubes as susceptor. The reactor design tackles the challenges accompanied by the carbothermal reduction of BOFS. High reduction rates of Fe and Cr as well as high P gasification rates have been achieved, exceeding the current state of the art.⁴⁻⁷ First assumptions indicated that Fe in BOFS has the most significant influence on the undesired phosphide formation mechanism. Therefore, an alternative process route has been introduced in Ponak (2019)⁶, reducing the Fe content in the slag to be treated. However, despite the depletion of Fe, lower P gasification rates could be achieved compared to the treatment of modified BOFS.⁶ Additionally, simulation outcomes made in FactSageTM corroborate the affinity between P and valuable metals during slag reduction.⁸

Materials and methods

In this work, synthetic slags with characteristic contents of either Fe, Cr, or Mn (4 m.-% or 17 m.-%) are examined after reduction. Thus, samples are prepared by mixing chemical powders (purity >97%) in the appropriate ratio with a basicity B_2 (ratio between m.-% CaO / m.-% SiO_2) of 1.4. The mixtures are heated in a MgO-crucible with a rate of 300 K/h in a resistance furnace up to 1873 K (holding time: 30 min). Then, obtained solidified slags are processed in a jaw-crusher to an adjusted grain size of ≤ 0.5 mm. Fine carbon powder is used as reductant, which is stoichiometrically determined with a surplus of 20%. Finally, the slag-carbon mixture is reduced in a MgO-

crucible with the same heating rate as for melting (holding time: 45 min) in a resistance furnace under argon gas purging of 4 L/min. Separated fractions after reduction are processed and weighed. The elementary analysis was quantified by ICP-OES for the synthetic slags and fractions after reduction. Moreover, the latter are additionally examined by SEM. The whole experimental procedure is summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Procedure of the experimental execution

Results and Discussion

Thermodynamic data for phosphide formation reactions presented in Schlesinger et al.⁹ were used for the representation of Gibbs energy (ΔG_f^0) vs. temperature, depicted in Figure 2, whereby the values given refer to one mole of the respective phosphide. Therefrom, Fe_2P , Cr_{12}P_7 , and Mn_3P_2 are most likely to be formed. Moreover, the red area defines the temperature range within the critical P-gasification due to the reduction of C_3P occurs, which in turn is lowered by the presence of SiO_2 .⁶

Figure 2: Gibb's energy vs. temperature for characteristic metal-phosphides, data from⁹

Melting was only successful for samples with higher amounts of Fe, Mn, and Cr. Thus, this contribution focuses on the results of these samples. Investigated fractions after reduction can be divided into a metal and a mineral phase. The iron-rich slag sample (S4) interacts strongly with the crucible, which leads to material leakage through the bottom of the crucible. However, metallic Fe could be recovered as well as metallic Cr from sample S5. In contrast, no metal phase formed for Mn-rich slag (S6), depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Treated material after carbothermal reduction at 1873 K – a) S4 b) S5 c) S6 and obtained fractions d) Fe-metal of S4 e) Cr-metal of S5 f) mineral phase of S6

According to Figure 4 a), the elemental compositions reveal that the mineral phase of S5 and S6 has strongly depleted in Cr and Mn. By contrast, high P amounts are bound into the metal of S4 and S5. Furthermore, SEM could still identify tiny metal droplets of Cr in the remaining mineral phase. Generally, a clear deviation in the behaviour between S5 and S6 could be determined. No metallic Mn could be obtained, but a segregation of the mineral phase took place: A Mn-rich dark mineral phase, in which nearly the whole P has accumulated and a pale calcium-silicate mineral phase poor in Mn. Mapping by SEM of a characteristic particle containing both phases of S6 is demonstrated in Figure 4 b).

Figure 4: Analysis results – a) ICP-OES b) SEM

Conclusion and prospects

Within an experimental series, the affinity between P and valuable metals such as Fe, Mn, and Cr was investigated during the carbothermal treatment of synthetic slag samples. All samples of small metal amounts (4 m.-% of Fe, Mn, and Cr) underlie a sintering process during melting and could not be reduced. This is not the case for samples with higher contents of Fe, Mn, and Cr, which results in a significant deviating behaviour. P preferably accumulates in the metal fraction of Fe and Cr bearing mixtures. In contrast, Mn could not be reduced, but segregation of the mineral phases took place, whereby P could be preferably found only in the Mn-enriched mineral phase. However, reduction conditions were not ideal due to the used furnace, crucible setup, and the lack of a graphite bed. Furthermore, the scope of slags consisting of all three metal species need to be the focus for further considerations in this field.

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